

Automating Digital Twin Creation for Humancentric Manufacturing Systems

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Introduction

In today's industrial landscape, the manufacturing sector faces considerable challenges that have a direct impact on productivity, efficiency, and overall performance. Digital Twins (DTs) have emerged to tackle these challenges, providing innovative solutions. However, when dealing with *humancentric manufacturing systems* that involve dominant active human participation, which is often driven by intrinsic motivation rather than strictly adhering to predefined protocols, additional challenges arise. The automation of DT creation for such systems is difficult due to uncertainties arising from human behaviors and the complexities associated with collecting relevant data. Moreover, issues such as imbalances in data representation and concerns regarding privacy further complicate the process. By leveraging machine-related manufacturing data, automated model extraction processes, such as process mining, can form the basis for the machine-related component of DT. To complete the DT, the integration of human-related processes is necessary, which is the goal of this research project.

Goal and Methodology

Goal: A framework and methodology for data-driven Digital Twins of humancentric manufacturing systems.

Challenges

Capture Change

The available data naturally changes over time and the system has to adjust as fast as possible while being resistant to noise.

Capture Human Steps

Tracking the important data points of the human steps has two major challenges:

1. Appropriate Sensors
2. Goal-oriented Work Process

Data Availability

The lack of prior data for humancentric steps might result in skewed data, thus, complicating the initial model creation.

Data Privacy

Data collection through work step tracking of humans has to be done in an ethical way to prevent data privacy issues.

Acknowledgment

The authors extend their thanks to the funding received from the ONE4ALL project funded by the European Commission, Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant Agreement No 101091877.

